

Supplementary materials to: Bikeability of road segments: an open, adjustable and extendible model

This repository contains data, code and results of the work presented in the paper "Bikeability of road segments: an open, adjustable and extendible model". With this document we provide an overview of the structure and contents.

In case you want to reference these supplementary materials please use the DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10724361](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724361). For NetAScore V1.0.1-fix, the DOI is [10.5281/zenodo.10666445](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666445)

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1. Code

- The Bikeability Model - **NetAScore**: V1.0.1-fix (file `1_netascore-1.0.1-fix.zip`). Code and documentation is also available on GitHub: <https://github.com/plus-mobilitylab/netascore/releases/tag/v1.0.1-fix>. For citation please refer to <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666445>.
- Code for the evaluation study: file `2_netascore-validation-main.zip` or <https://github.com/plus-mobilitylab/netascore-validation>
 - Code for sampling of street-level imagery based on NetAScore output (stratified random sample across bikeability classes)
 - Assessment of survey and conference results including plot generation.

2. Data

- **Bikeability assessment** with NetAScore V1.0.1-fix (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10666445>)
 - Input **network data** from OpenStreetMap: files `osm_salzburg.xml` and `osm_wuppertal.xml` within `osm_input` directory
 - Digital elevation models (DEMs) are available as open data:
 - For Salzburg/Austria as GeoTIFF download: <https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/en/dataset/b5de6975-417b-4320-afdb-eb2a9e2a1dbf>
 - For Wuppertal via OGC WCS (Web Coverage Service): https://www.wcs.nrw.de/geobasis/wcs_nw_dgm?REQUEST=GetCapabilities&SERVICE=WCS
 - **Assessed networks** (NetAScore output): files `netascore_salzburg.gpkg` and `netascore_wuppertal.gpkg`
- **Image sampling**: road segments and location of sampled images (including metadata) are provided in `salzburg_sample.gpkg` and `wuppertal_sample.gpkg` within `2_image_sampling`. The column `removed` for edges indicates images that were removed from the sampling set during manual filtering. For details on the sampling process and manual filtering please check the documentation at <https://github.com/plus-mobilitylab/netascore-validation>.

3. Images

The directory `3_images` contains all **60 images used in the evaluation study**. Files are named according to their ID which consists of the place name, bikeability class and sample identifier.

4. Results

- Responses of the **online survey** are provided in `1_online_survey.csv`. Column names as well as response values should be self-explanatory.
 - Columns named by image IDs contain the numeric (integer) values of ratings. A value of `0` indicates infrastructure rated unsuitable, with `100` being the best possible rating.
 - For preserving anonymity of respondents, we re-sampled the year of birth to 10 year increments.
 - Columns `continue_p#` refer to whether participants opted to continue rating another page of 10 images (`yes`) or opted out (`no`). In case of no answer (empty column), the survey proceeded (unless answered `no` on a previous page).
- Quantitative **image ratings** from the CRBAM conference (numeric suffix of column names refers to the modeled bikeability class)
 - digitized ratings from the two **workshop** sessions are provided in `2_img_workshop.csv`
 - digitized results of images available **throughout the conference** (in the so-called "arena") are available in `3_img_conference-arena.csv`
- Digitized results of **indicator ratings** and proposed new indicators are provided in `4_indicators_workshop`. These results were generated during both conference workshops.
- Photographic documentation of the workshop outcomes is available in `5_workshop_documentation`. This contains both indicator ratings as well as image ratings with qualitative feedback.
- Photographic documentation of image ratings collected in the conference arena are found in `6_conference-arena_documentation`.
- Figures of the paper are included in the subdirectory `7_figures`.
- In `8_detail_plots` we provide plots of survey ratings per image with modeled bikeability visualized as red line.
- A summary of expert ratings and feedback per image from the conference workshop is provided in `9_expert-feedback-summary.pdf`.

5. Full set of image samples

Here we provide all images considered during the sampling process. Images that were filtered out are contained in the subdirectory `bin`. The directories `c1` to `c5` contain images eligible for final random sampling per bikeability class. For details on the sampling process please read the documentation at <http://github.com/plus-mobilitylab/netascore-validation>.